

IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 1 MATHEMATICS LEARNERS USING DIGITAL MODULES

Gellie H. Repato

Aguilar Integrated School, Aguilar District, Schools Division Office I Pangasinan, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14201996>

ABSTRACT

The study was conducted at Aguilar Integrated School during the School Year 2021 – 2022 aimed to propose supplementary learning material in improving the math skills of Grade 1 learners to further and efficiently teach the most essential learning competencies covered for the Fourth Quarter. The descriptive research design was employed to this study. The researcher made use of pre-experimental methods of research. It is one–group pretest-posttest design. Based on the findings of the study, the teacher-researcher therefore concludes that the achievement level of 30 learners (30) who took the pre-test prior to the use of digital drill modules was unsatisfactory. The result was the indicator of low performance of grade one learners. After 8 weeks of teaching intervention using the digital modules, the learner’s achievement skills were improved to excellence. The researcher provided supplementary instructional materials which had motivated their interest to participate and engaged in the learning sessions. They were greatly enlightened about the lesson with help of the digital modules. Results showed that Digital Modules as a supplemental tool played a vital role in this kind of new normal teaching and learning modalities. Furthermore, it showed positive feedback to the learners and parents to have this kind of intervention in imparting the support for the teacher in learning at home in this time of pandemic

Keywords: *Improve, Digital, Supplement, Modules, Performance*

INTRODUCTION

The pandemic brought by the coronavirus is one of the developing global crises in the public health. The fight against its threats has received massive global attention on how to eradicate the continual increase of growing infections (Guo, et al., 2020). As the World Health Organization (WHO) stated that COVID-19 is already a pandemic, the Philippines was placed in a state of calamity under the Presidential Proclamation No. 929 s. 2020. Suspension and temporary closing of companies, enterprises and business operations has taken effect. Restrictions were implemented on the movement of people, goods, and services within and across municipal borders were imposed. Different measures were suggested to control the spread of the infection and lessen the death rate such as social distancing, wearing of face masks, handwashing, self-isolation, and improved health care system by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2020).

One of the sectors most shaken by the Covid-19 pandemic is education, affecting the lives of students in the country since March 2020. Schools have closed and face-to-face classes have been suspended in an attempt to stem the spread of the coronavirus. The initial government response was to impose community quarantine and to suspend classes disrupted school learning in Luzon and later the rest of the country.

The remaining days of school year 2019-2020, students were required to accomplish academic requirements at home and teachers were required to provide assignments in lieu of classroom teaching. Several schools have adopted other modes of delivery such as distance learning platforms.

To provide and sustain quality education despite lockdowns and community quarantine, the new normal has to be taken into consideration. As President Rodrigo Duterte had stated he would not allow face-to-face classes in the absence of any vaccine against Covid-19, the Department of Education (DepEd) and stakeholders developed a Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) school year 2020-2021 to ensure continuing education. The BE-LCP is a package of education interventions that will enable students to continue learning and teachers to deliver instruction amid the Covid-19 threat. The BE-CLP provides several learning delivery modalities that are being adopted by different schools in the country.

These are face-to-face learning, distance learning (with three types: modular distance learning, online distance learning, and television/radio-based instruction), blended learning and home schooling. Schools can adopt one or a combination of these modes, depending on the Covid-19 restrictions as well as the context of the learners in the school or locality. The COVID-19 pandemic led educators to distance learning education readiness.

According to Phan & Dang (2017), factors such as training, attitude, technical competence, time constraints, pedagogy, and methodology were among the major distance learning education elements. In a study conducted by Ventayen (2019) on the readiness of DepEd Teachers to distance learning, showed that despite the limited

experience such as technical skills, time management, knowledge and attitude in online education, they were still able to cope with the trends in distance learning.

As this pandemic is slated to exist until the preventive vaccine is discovered, it is essential to know how the educators who are the prime facilitators of the education adjusted to this transition and what challenges they faced while adapting to this transition as their preparedness for the coming times. Amid the threat of Covid-19, Aguilar Integrated School has adapted to printed modular distance learning.

The school has distinct needs and has to adjust to what is necessary in its situation. After the conduct of a survey on the possible learning delivery modalities, modular printed distance learning emerged as the most preferred by the school and considered the sole remedy to reach students. Other learning delivery methods are found not feasible because of difficult internet access or slow signal and non-availability of gadgets needed by learners and teachers. These have affected adoption of other learning modes other than modular printed learning. Although some households have the requisite devices such as smart phones and computers, they are hampered by slow internet connections and signals as well as daily costs of prepaid loads.

Teaching and learning in “new normal” comes in different styles and forms. Educators are now experimenting on the new methods on teaching and learning which aim at improving the quality of education and the quality of citizens produced by schools. As new styles and forms of teaching and learning arrive, it also has advantages and disadvantages as well. Printed modular learning is the most preferred modality of learning in Aguilar. All kinds of subjects are being taught through modules and that includes Mathematics.

Digital Modules as learning module is another alternative way to teach Math concepts. In addition to printed modules, teachers were required to be creative in collecting learning resources and creating media needed for teaching and learning process. The use of modules in learning can help the student in solving problems independently (Christiyoda et al, 2016). Digital modules are innovations that can be used by teachers in solving the problems of Government-issued module or textbook. These innovations can be done by utilizing the development of IT technology in schools.

Mathematics, in general, is an important subject because of its practical role to a person and the society as a whole. Learning math is about more than just taking a medicine; it's at the core of everything that exists, including us.

Good (1975) as cited Yazon (2016) modular approach is modernizing way of teaching process suited to learners to advance at their own best rate through passing the necessary instruction and satisfying their needs, thus in individual cases, will be able to earn their degree in considerably shorter period of time.

According to Espinosa (2015) the modular self-paced instruction is a kind of modular approach wherein the student studies all concepts written in the module by himself, by his own effort and by his own understanding.

Locally, teaching mathematics poses a great challenge among Grade I teachers. Despite of the fact that the Grade I teachers have undergone series of seminars in the use of various strategies and modalities in the delivery of instruction to Grade I learners in the “new normal” setting, still there is a doubt on the minds of the teachers as to its effectiveness. Needless to say, the lack of resources for Mathematics instruction is also another factor.

Thus, the researcher embarked on developing digital modules in Math as a supplement to the Alternative Delivery Mode Modules provided by the Department of Education for distance learning modality. This improved learning and remedy the least mastered skills of the Grade I learners. The researcher prepared the digital modules and were given individually to the Grade I learners. The modules were used once a week, every Monday and the outputs were retrieved every Friday. Furthermore, the self-learning digital modules were intended to re-teach the concept(s) and skill(s) to help the learners master a competency-based skill which they were not able to develop using solely the printed modular approach.

Digital module as a medium for teaching and learning is one of the largest changes in recent years which presents addition of technology education facilities in a teaching instructional method. Brown and Atkins (2016) stated that when designing modules, it is essential for teachers to be aware of concepts of deep and surface approaches to learning. Many researches have previously been conducted on the relationship between courses and the approach students take to learning and found positive relationship between curriculum and learning approaches.

The goal of the modules is to provide resources to teachers that will allow them to transform their classrooms into active, student-centered learning environments. According to Stewart and Wilkerson (1999), the common characteristics of a module can be distinguished that it is self-contained, independent instruction unit, systematically organized, well defined have a means of evaluating the work.

Today, Mathematics is not just a subject in the school but a springboard of scientific and technological evolution. Scientists and Mathematicians who are toiling hard to accelerate the technologies and scientific progress feel the great need of Mathematics. Man learns to use the things around him, not for himself alone but also for his fellowmen. As life advances, he discovers many things like the nuclear energy, wonder drugs, space probes and computers. All these testify technological growth in life. Realizing the key role played by Mathematics in the advancement of civilization and modernization, educators make it imperative that pupils show how adequate knowledge of it and acquire sufficient Mathematics proficiency.

It is apparent that a teacher has to be creative and resourceful to be able to tailor his instructional materials to the needs and capacities of the learners. What the pupils

learn depend largely on the ability, competency and skills of the teacher to prepare and use instructional material so as to capture learner 's attention, spark their interest and develop their skills and hidden talents. One of the techniques to achieve these is to make use of the digital modules in Mathematics which the researcher wanted to assess its effectiveness.

Today, as the Philippines struck by the Coronavirus threat, and where one of the sectors most alarmed by this is education, schools have closed and face-to-face classes have been suspended in an attempt to curb the spread of the coronavirus affecting the lives of students in the country. The initial government response was to impose community quarantine and to suspend classes that disrupted school learning in Luzon and later the rest of the country. This paves a breakthrough in both private and public institutions to adopt other modes of delivery such as distance learning platforms to continue serve the school children. For the remainder of school year 2019-2020, learners have started fulfilling academic requirements at home and teachers were required to provide assignments in lieu of classroom teaching.

Along with the mandate of President Rodrigo Duterte stressed disallowing face-to-face set-up and encouraging educational reforms to ensure that every Filipino child is safe at home. To provide and sustain quality education despite lockdowns and community quarantine, the new normal has to be taken into consideration, the Department of Education (DepEd) and stakeholders developed a Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) school year 2020-2021 is one concrete response to reverse the decline of our country's economy and to move towards its goal of long-terms educational reform and sustainable economic growth. The BE-LCP is a package of education interventions that will enable students to continue learning and teachers to deliver instruction amid the Covid-19 threat. The BE-CLP provides several learning delivery modalities that are being adopted by different schools in the country. These are face-to-face learning, distance learning (with three types: modular distance learning, online distance learning, and television/radio-based instruction), blended learning and home schooling. Schools can adopt one or a combination of these modes, depending on the Covid-19 restrictions as well as the context of the learners in the school or locality.

Magsambol (2020) reported that Philippines ranked bottom in the international test in Science and Mathematics on the concluded Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) which were given to elementary pupils on 2019. Out of 25 participating countries we ranked 23rd the lowest scores were registered in math, science and reading. It was revealed that out of 131 competencies/skills only 31 skills were learned by the children. The data disclosed that our students are not really performing well on those identified core subjects. The critical thinking, creative thinking and reasoning abilities which are the primary concern of the K-12 curriculum were not given emphasis during teaching –learning process. Thus, further educational reforms, more innovations and careful planning are needed to attain the substantial improvement which we have always been working intensively to meet its goals.

On the other hand, the achievement rate of the Grade 1 learners in Math Diagnostic Test at Aguilar Integrated School during the school year 2019-2020 during the first and second quarter before the pandemic is quite alarming as the mean percentage score is only 39.45% (which means that majority of the learners are under low proficient). The result is quite far from the national percentage set forth by the Department of Education. Moreover, the results disclosed that students do not possess sufficient math skills and competencies. The learners generally do not get adequate instructional time or time on task; teachers focused more on covering material instead of building conceptual understanding of science concepts. These factors had yielded a low performing result.

Consequently, the first periodical assessment through distance learning modality result of the Grade 1 learners for the school year 2020-2021 is quite unimpressive as the mean percentage scores is 45.56% which way below from the set national standard rating of 80%. On the other hand, the researcher observed that the learners displayed an insignificant performance in their activity worksheets, printed modules and among others. The performance is quite disappointing to note as our agency has so much expectation from our learners to be equipped with necessary skills which they could make use as support for a life-long learning skills.

The Aguilar Integrated School is one of the public schools which have implementing the printed and digital modular distance learning program. The school has distinct needs and has to adjust to what is necessary in its situation. After the conduct of a survey on the possible learning delivery modalities, printed and digital modular distance learning emerged as the most preferred by the school and considered the sole remedy to reach students.

Although some households have the requisite devices such as smart phones and computers, they are hampered by slow internet connections and signals as well as daily costs of prepaid loads. Teachers are now experimenting on the new methods on teaching and learning which aim at improving the quality of education and the quality of citizens produced by schools. As new styles and forms of teaching and learning arrive, it also has advantages and disadvantages as well. Printed modular learning is the most preferred modality of learning in the said school. The use of digital modules is also given to learners who have access to gadgets as supplemental tool for learning. All kinds of subjects are being taught through printed and digital modules and worksheets and that includes Mathematics.

The research proponent who has been teaching the subject Mathematics observes that learners have different learning styles in understanding the Math lesson. The delivery of instruction using printed modular distance learning becomes ineffective if activities are not developmentally appropriate and becomes less participative and engaging which affects the mastery learning competencies and the performance become less effective. In conclusion, the teacher should consider the learners' needs in the teaching-learning process where more supplemental and engaging activities should be given to elevate the

performance of learners in the “new normal” setting. One way of addressing what interest them is providing them learning opportunities which bridges them to the right learning.

The research proponent is a teacher it is in her desire, to foresee an improved academic achievement of grade 1 learners in the future and believing that through research, wanted to determine the efficacy of digital modules in improving their Math performance level at Aguilar Integrated School during the fourth quarter of academic year 2021- 2022. To further investigate, the action research entitled “*Improving the Performance of Grade 1 Mathematics Learners Using Digital Modules*” was conducted in the study.

Research Questions

This research aimed to determine the effect of using digital modules in the delivery of instruction in Mathematics of Grade I learners. It was conducted at Aguilar Integrated School, Aguilar District, school year 2021-2022. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following sub- problems:

1. What is the performance of the Grade I Mathematics learners before the intervention?
2. What is the performance of the Grade I Mathematics learners after the intervention?
3. Is there a significant difference on the performance of Grade I Mathematics learners before and after the intervention?

METHODOLOGY

a. Participants and/or other Sources of Data and Information

The researcher used simple random sampling wherein the respondents were selected based on their academic performance during the 3rd quarter assessment. A total of 30 learners out of 35 learners in Grade 1 in Aguilar Integrated School were chosen as respondents based from the results of their 3rd Summative test in Math. The result of the Diagnostic Teacher –Made Test (Third Quarter) was used for the selection of the sample population of the learner-respondents. The result bears the following information: that out of 35 learners, 5 of them scored 75% mastery level as set by DepEd, and the remaining 30 learners scored below the required the level of mastery. These are the learners from the Grade 1 - Matagumpay comprising of eighteen (18) boys and twelve (12) girls who posted a score 74% and below the standard level of mastery.

b. Data Gathering Methods

The standardized pre-test and post-test was used in the study. The researcher requested permission to conduct the study from the Schools Division Superintendent and School Principal. The researcher administered the pre-test to the respondents. From the results, the teacher used the digital module in Mathematics to improve the Mathematics

performance of the Grade I learners. The tablets provided by the Department of Education in the school were used for the digital modules. The digital modules were used a supplemental tool in addition to the ADM modules prescribed by the DepEd. The gathered data were tallied, analyzed and interpreted. There were also activities and exercises given before the posttest. At the end of the quarter, Posttest was conducted to determine the performance of the Grade I learners in Math.

The instrument was submitted to the school principal, master teacher and math coordinator using the five (5) point Likert-scale for content validation. Given a balanced set of choices, the data on the performance of the learners in Mathematics will identified and interpreted. The pre-test and post-test results of the learners were interpreted using also a (5) point Likert Scale. The Likert scale in the pre-test and post-test in the research used the descriptive ratings and equivalence of 17-20, very proficient, 13-16, proficient, 9-12, nearly proficient, 5-8, low proficient, and 0-4, not proficient.

The evaluators' comments and suggestions were considered for the refinement of the instrument. The approved research instrument was administered during pre and post assessment which aimed to improve the performance of Grade 1 Mathematics learners.

Descriptive statistics such as mean and MPS was used to treat the level of performance of the Grade I learners in Mathematics. T-test was used to process the data and find out how effective the digital module instruction in improving the performance level of Grade I Mathematics learners.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the data for the performance of grade 1 learners in Math before and after using digital modules were analyzed and interpreted. The study considered the results from performance of the learners in their assessment/ pretest and the least learned skills of the respondents in Math. Thus, the effectiveness of using Digital modules in improving the performance of grade 1 pupils in Math was analyzed. The succeeding tables present the results of the study.

Level of Performance of Grade I learners in Mathematics in the Pretest and Posttest

Digital Modules provide learners with multiple pathways to learning. As the number of computer-based activities increase in classrooms, learners are provided with immense opportunities to engage in a variety of learning modalities (i.e., visual, auditory, and/or kinesthetic) during the learning process (Brent, 2015). Digital modules as infused in technology and curriculum had immense impact on children's learning and support overall educational goals. Learners are also provided with a set of learning tools to assist them in achieving developmental academic goals across the curriculum.

Table 1 shows the level of performance in Math of the Grade 1 learners in the pretest and posttest. It can be gleaned on table 1 that the level of performance in Math of the Grade 1 learners in the pretest has the mean of 8.4 with a descriptive equivalence of “poor” and post-test has the mean of 18.17 in a twenty (20) item test with a descriptive equivalence of “excellent”. The data implies that inadequacy of instructional resources and absence of hands-on experiences due to the sole use of printed modules and worksheets as teaching and learning modality are some of the deterrent factors which affect the overall academic performance of the respondents. Inappropriate and meaningful teaching strategy suited to their learning needs and capabilities are other common issues why teaching and learning process become unsuccessful. Moreover, the following probable causes identified by the researcher are as follows: lack of enthusiasm to learn and apply the new math concepts because of the “new normal” modality of learning, inappropriate use of teaching approaches and strategies in Math, and inadequate instructional materials in teaching the subject because of distance learning.

Table 1

Level of Performance in Math of the Grade 1 Learners in the Pretest and Post-test

Scores (HPS=20)	Pretest (Mean= 8.40; SD= 1.35)			Post-test (Mean= 18.17; SD= 1.63)		
	N	%	DE*	N	%	DE*
17-20	0	0	Very Proficient	23	76.67%	Very Proficient
13-16	0	0	Proficient	7	23.33%	Proficient
9-12	15	50%	Nearly Proficient	0	0	Nearly Proficient
5-8	15	50%	Low Proficient	0	0	Low Proficient
0-4	0	0	Not Proficient	0	0	Not Proficient
TOTAL	30	100%		30	100%	

**DE- Descriptive equivalent*

If the problem will not be addressed the learners’ performance will continue to decline. Teacher should make the necessary teaching adjustment pertaining to the enhancement of the learners’ academic performance geared to higher learning outcomes. Teachers should apply differentiated instruction that could provide the different needs, strengths, and abilities of the learners to have an accurate result of the performance of the learners.

After the use of digital modules, the level of performance of Grade 1 learners increased as shown in the mean of the posttest equals to 18.17. A critical analysis of the means suggests that learners who used digital modules have good performance in the post- test. The data also shows that significant improvements were generated after the employing the said intervention and responded to learners' readiness, instructional needs, interests and learning preferences and provides opportunities to work in varied instructional formats.

According to Dario (2016), digital modules are well suited as a supplementary aid for math skills and capable of presenting activities that are interesting and motivating to learners—including the use of pictorial displays and positive feedbacks.

Furthermore, according to a summary of current research and educator surveys, the use of digital modules aid in the development of a common base of knowledge among learners, enhances learners' problem-solving skills, provides greater accommodation of diverse learning styles, and increases student motivation and enthusiasm and promotes teacher effectiveness (Lopez, 2017)

Significant Difference between the Level of Performance in Math of the Grade 1 Learners in the Pretest and Posttest

The table below shows the significant difference between the level of performance of Grade I learners in Math before and after the intervention using the digital modules.

Table 2

Significant Difference Between the Level of Performance in Math of the Grade 1 Learners in the Pretest and Posttest

Performance	Mean	T value	t-critical value	Decision
Pretest	8.4	-24.76	-2.024	Significant
Posttest	18.17			

Table 2 shows the significant difference between the level of performance of Grade 1 Mathematics learners in the pretest and posttest. It also reveals that the t-computed is equal to -24.76 which is beyond the t-critical value equals to -2.024 at @.05. This implies that there was a significant difference between the posttest and pretest results. Thus, it only reveals that there is an improvement in the level of performance of grade 1 Mathematics learners after using digital modules based on the results computed.

The study of Capuno et. al. (2019) recommended that teachers must always use instructional media as part of their teaching routines such as presentation of lesson, learning activities, and evaluation to make a more meaningful learning.

It also shown in the interpretation that the learners increased the score with the help of digital modules as a supplemental tool of their learning together with their parent. It was supported by the study of Sumaoang (2020), stated that teachers should re-evaluate the modules, and they have to make sure that all the lesson or activities are appropriate to the needs of the learners.

It can be reflected that digital modules as supplemental tool may be employed by the teachers to enhance the academic performance of the learners. They may adapt it as a resource to the teaching and learning process. In this time of new normal in education, teachers must be creative and find ways to help learners and use appropriate instructional materials which can aid them in the familiarity to a given situation and acquitted them to different method and solutions that can be applied to higher math skills and real-life circumstances.

Furthermore, Digital Modules should be crafted with considerations on the learners' learning style, interests, strengths, and weaknesses and be made as intervention to improve the math skills of the learners particularly in solving problems. It is also recommended that teachers should integrate digital modules in the teaching-learning process in other areas to improve the achievement level of the learners. A school-based in-service training should be done intended to teach teachers on how to utilize the digital modules in the teaching and learning process.

Finally, the use of digital modules can also build rapport between the teachers and learners to maintain a connection where learners can feel that there is still a teacher who facilitates learning with them even, they are in their home learning situation.

Recommendations

1. With Grade 1 students performing better, it is recommended to expand into other grade levels the use of digital modules. Subsequent research might investigate the effectiveness of digital modules to increase student achievement in different grade levels or content areas, allowing teachers an understanding as to whether similar gains may be realized beyond Grade 1. Greater variety in the requirements of students across grade levels might also necessitate following learner engagement, content curation and improving areas from a broader position.
2. Finally, while the literature emphasizes differentiated instruction as key to addressing students' diversity and learning styles, future research should also be devoted to crafting digital modules that are designed using differentiated instruction based on current technology theory strategies. For instance, building learning content that is modular and flexible to each learners readiness levels as well as their interest areas and the way they like to learn it best. Assessing the relative utility of such digitally differentiated modules may yield new insights into how this type of material directly supports variation in individual learner needs, and even lead to improvements for an expanded set of competencies crucial to academic performance.
3. This work should be expanded upon with additional research into the long term effects that digital modules can exert on learners' performance as well better understanding

of how caregivers might prove integral in helping to support and learn alongside their young child while engaging with these modules. Long-term study to track students academic growth, especially in mathematics as we have found improvement in Grade 1 math performance using digital module and how it could help them retain knowledge. Examining the role of parental support in increasing module effectiveness could also help educators and content developers create instruction media that are more family-centric. E-learning modules could be done this way to make sure that technology-driven learning resources will work while students figure out how an institution or support network can fit around them.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in full compliance with ethical standards to ensure the protection and well-being of all participants. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from the students and their guardians, outlining the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and the voluntary nature of their participation. Participants were assured that their responses would remain confidential and anonymous, and that the data collected would be used solely for academic and research purposes. The study did not involve any physical or psychological risks, and participants were free to withdraw from the research at any point without any negative consequences. Furthermore, the research adhered to institutional guidelines for ethical conduct in research and was reviewed and approved by the appropriate ethics review board to ensure adherence to ethical principles in educational research, such as respect for persons, beneficence, and justice.

REFERENCES

- Brent , V. (2020). Home Learning in Times of COVID: Experiences of Parents, 2020. *Journal of New Normal Education*, 7, 34-38
- Brown, J. & Atkins, K (2016). A descriptive analysis of first grade division instruction in basal mathematics programs: Violations of pedagogy. *Journal of Behavioral Education*, 6, 381-403.
- Capuno, R., Revalde, H., Etcuban, J. O., Aventuna, M., Medio, G., & Demeterio, R. A. (2019). Facilitating Learning Mathematics Through the Use of Instructional Media. *INTERNATIONAL ELECTRONIC JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICS EDUCATION*, 14(3), 677–688. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/5785>
- Christiyoda, S., Widoretno, S., & Karyanto, P. (n.d.). PENGEMBANGAN MODUL BERBASIS KEMAMPUAN PEMECAHAN MASALAH PADA MATERI SISTEM EKSRESI UNTUK MENINGKATKAN BERPIKIR KRITIS. *INKUIRI Jurnal Pendidikan IPA*, 5(1), 74–84. <https://doi.org/10.20961/inkuiri.v5i1.9510>
- Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic. (2024, October 29). Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/europe/emergencies/situations/covid-19>
- Dario, M. (2016), Pretest and posttest design, Retrieved: 01.09. 2010 experiment resource from <http://www.experimentresources6m/pretest-postest-designs.html>
- Espinosa, R. (2015). *Teaching student’s math skill in the classrooms*. Boston: Espinosa & Bacon.

- Guo, Y., Cao, Q., Hong, Z., Tan, Y., Chen, S., Jin, H., . . . Yan, Y. (2020). The origin, transmission and clinical therapies on coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) outbreak – an update on the status. *Military Medical Research*, 7(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40779-020-00240-0>
- Lopez, R. (2017). How young is too young to teach numeracy? Retrieved November 2021 from <https://www.waterford.org/education/how-young-is-too-young-to-teach-math/>
- Magsambol, B. (2020, December 12). PH lowest among 58 countries in math, science – global assessment. *RAPPLER*. Retrieved from <https://www.rappler.com>
- Phan, T. T. N., & Dang, L. T. T. (2017). Teacher Readiness for Online Teaching: A Critical Review*. *International Journal on Open and Distance e-Learning*, 3(1). Retrieved from <https://ijodel.upou.edu.ph/index.php/ijodel/article/view/18>
- Stewart, J. L., & Wilkerson, V. L. (1999). *ChemConnections: A Guide to Teaching with Modules*. Retrieved from <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=7f7bb0a1ebbfcf6acceae954d8477b8929c1628>
- Sumaoang, J. (2020) . The Implementation of Modular Distance Learning in the Phil.Secondary Public Schools retrieved 2021 from <http://www.secondaryeducation.com/educational-video/education-and-video.php>
- Ventayen, R. J. M. (2019). Teachers' Readiness in Online Teaching Environment: A Case of Department of Education Teachers. *Journal of Education, Management and Social Sciences*. *Journal of Education, Management and Social Sciences*, 2(1), 94–106. Retrieved from <https://ijsemss.psu.edu.ph/index.php/1/article/view/71>
- Yazon, A. D. (2016). Validation and Effectiveness of Module in Assessment of Students Learning. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*.